

DYNAMIC FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF ALUMINUM HONEYCOMB COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Impact behaviors of Aluminum Honeycombs Composites(AHC) by drop weight test were investigated in this study. Two types of specimens with 1/2" and 1/4" cell size were tested by two impactors with the weight of 5.25kg_f and 11.9kg_f respectively. Transient, contact and elastic-plastic analyses were performed by finite element method. Impact behavior of AHC about impact sites appeared nearly the same in low impact energy, but it was different in high impact energy. Face was the strongest about impact and short-edge was the weakest. The damaged area of AHC was enlarged with the increase of impactor weight that is corresponding to impact energy. After 3-point bending test, fracture modes of AHC were analyzed with AE counts, lower face sheet was fractured in the long-edge direction first, and then separation between face sheet and core happened. In the short-edge direction after core wrinkled, lower face sheet was torn, impact behavior by FE analysis were increased localized damage in high velocity because the faster velocity of the impact was, the smaller the stress of core was. Consequently, impactor weight had an effect on widely damaged area, while the impact velocity gave rise to localized damaged area.

KEYWORDS: Aluminum honeycomb sandwich panel, Hexagon, Face sheet, Core, Drop weight impact test, 3-point bending test, FEM

INTRODUCTION

Aluminum honeycomb sandwich panels (AHSP) have been widely used in the fields of aerospace, defense, automotive, railway, marine, communication and sport industry for the merits of light weight, high strength and high stiffness. But AHSP shows it's vulnerable before impact force. David M. McGowan et al. represented that manufacturing defect would happen to AHSP caused by careless impact[1]. This damage almost didn't mark on the face sheet externally but it would cause strength reduction internally. It was also stated that the conditions and degrees of impact damage were variable according to the test methods such as drop weight impact test and air-gun test etc. S. Santosa and T. Wiezbicki compared the impact strength between the honeycomb cell and foam. They found that the aluminum honeycomb could own better impact behavior than aluminum foam under unidirectional loading and a combined load of compressive and bending[2]. T. Y. Reddy et al.(1998) analyzed the impact conformation with the experiential equation derived. S. D. Papka et al.(1997) evaluated the damage mechanism after impacting by optical analysis and ultrasonic c-scan. M. K. Kim et al. found that test frequency is lower than resonance frequency of honeycomb structure by using mechanical impedance method in spite of various ways of finding the debonding honeycomb structure[3-6]. Beomkeun Kim et al. calculated the elastic modulus, shear modulus, Poisson's ratio, compressive bending strength, shear bending strength and flexibility of the sort of cell.

In his research triangular and star cell was weak compressive bending strength and shear bending strength[7]. But it had high flexibility.

In our previous work the variable fracture mode was found corresponding to the increase of impact energy. The change of fracture mode could be measured by the impact energy loss rate. Cheng-Zorn Tsai et al.(1998) developed Green's function to analyze the upper and lower part of a honeycomb sandwich panel subjected to low velocity impact[8]. S. Thwaites et al. examined the fracture behavior of honeycomb sandwich structure using elastic wave and acoustic emission[9]. Werner Goldsmith et al. checked buckling pattern of core and analyzed small elastic energy after AHSP, aluminum core and flex core were impacted[10]. These studies promoted the research of composite honeycomb sandwich panel. But the study of aluminum honeycomb sandwich panel was subject to be developed with consideration of the effect of impact position, weight and velocity.

In this study a typical impact fracture mode was evaluated. The analysis of the impact energy caused during the damage of impacted specimens was also stated. Fracture modes of AHSP were analyzed with AE counts according to 3-point bending test. Impact damage area was observed with ultrasonic c-scan. Nonlinear impact analysis is carried ANSYS 5.5.

FUNDAMENTAL THEORY

Energy calculations

T. Y. Reddy analogized the result of conical type with hemispherical type using exponential equation[3]. As shown in Fig.1. The work done in creating the lip can be expressed by the integral from with the differential element of circumferential length of $2\pi r$ and cross-sectional area of $t_0 \cdot dr$.

$$W = \int_0^{R_0} 2\pi t_0 \sigma_y r \ln \frac{R_0}{r} dr = \frac{1}{2} \pi R_0^2 t_0 \sigma_y \quad (1)$$

By the conical type impactor, the absorbed energy can be calculated using the work in the perforation of a plate with consideration of the shape coefficient.

$$W = \lambda \frac{1}{2} \pi R_0^2 t_0 \sigma_y \quad (2)$$

Total energy in the procedure of perforation is the sum of kinetic, potential and absorbed energy.

$$E_t = E_k + E_p + E_a \quad (3)$$

Where the absorbed energy is

$$\begin{aligned} E_a &= mgh + \frac{1}{2} m(v_0^2 - v^2) \\ &= \lambda \frac{1}{2} \pi R_0^2 t_0 \sigma_y = W \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Fig. 1 Perforation of a thin plate by conical-ended tup

When conical impactor impacts on AHSP, work in the perforation is about 57J. Face one of impact sites is 45J. Long-edge one of impact sites is 33j. Point one of impact sites is 33J. Therefore, shape coefficients of impact sites are 1.27 at face, 1.63 at long-edge, 1.73 at point and short-edge.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD AND FEM ANALYSIS

Materials of the specimens

Impact behaviors of Aluminum Honeycombs Sandwich Panel (AHSP) by drop weight test are investigated in this part. AHSPs with hexagonal-cell shape are fabricated by A 3003H14 sheet from HANKUK FIBER.LTD. Bondex is used for adhesive. Mechanical properties of the Aluminum plate (A3003H14) and tup (SS400) are listed in table.1.

Two types of specimens with 1/2" and 1/4" size cell are tested by two impactors with the weight of 5.25kg_f and 11.9kg_f respectively. Dimension of impact specimen is 100mm×100mm×6mm. Thickness of upper face sheet is 1mm and that of lower face sheet is 0.5mm. The height of core is 4.5mm and thickness of it is 0.0762mm.

Table.1 Mechanical Properties of Aluminum Plate (A 3003H14) and tup (SS400)

	σ_u (MPa)	σ_{ys} (MPa)	ϵ (%)	E (GPa)	ρ (g/cm ³)
A 3003H14	185	150	16	69	2.73
SS400	400	235	20	210	7.85

AHSP for 3-point bending test is formed by face sheet and core bonded together by adhesive.

Experimental method

The 3-point bending test is executed to check the impact mode. 1/2"size cell specimens were tested along the long-edge and short-edge directions while 1/4"size cell specimens were tested irrespective of bending direction. As shown in Fig. 2. During the 3-point bending test, AE signal was analyzed about fracture mode by displacement controls. The dimension of the bending specimen was 250mm×70mm×6mm according to ASTM 393-94.

Fig. 2 Schematic diagram of apparatus for 3 point bending and AE experiment

As shown in Fig. 3(a), Dynatup GRC8250 drop tower is driven by Instron to finish the impact test. Impact behaviors of AHSP are examined according to the parameter changes such as the weight or initial position of the impactor. In Fig. 3(b), the spherical tup with the diameter of 12.7mm (1/2") is used for impact. AHSP is fixed at the center of the clamp with a 75mm diameter hole.

Fig. 3 Drop weight impact test and specimen fixture

A:face , B: long-edge, C: short-edge, D : point
 l)long-edge direction, s) short-edge direction

Fig. 4 Impact position and bending direction

For considering the effect of weight 5.25kg_f and 11.9kg_f impactors are used with the considering the sum of crosshead and tup weight. Impact sites are chosen at face, long-edge, short-edge and point in order to observe, as shown in Fig. 4, the impact effects of face sheet and core. As shown in table. 2, AHSP is impacted corresponding to the impact energy of 10J, 19J, 32J and 43J respectively.

Table.2 Impact height and impact velocity of 11.9kg_f and 5.25kg_f impactors

Impact weight	Parameter	10J	19J	32J	43J
11.9kg _f	Impact height (cm)	8.6	16.3	27.4	36.9
	Impact velocity (m/s)	1.3	1.78	2.32	2.69
5.25kg _f	Impact height (cm)	19.5	37	62	83.5
	Impact velocity (m/s)	1.95	2.69	3.49	4.05

FEM analysis

The impact process is simulated numerically using a finite element method by ANSYS 5.5 with nonlinear FE code. The meshed model for 1/4 symmetric condition is shown in Fig. 5. The model is all constrained except for y direction. AHSP is full constrained because of the fixture of clamp. In contact analysis, the contact pairs are formed by target and contact surface. The upper face sheet of chosen for AHSP Target surface, and the external area of tup is chosen for contact surface. Yielding stress and tangent modulus of tup and AHSP are inputted for elastic-plastic analysis. The tup with the weight of 11.9kg_f and 5.25kg_f contacts AHSP with the initial velocity of $v_0 = \sqrt{2gh}$. The commercial program ANSYS 5.5 is applied to analyze the relation between the time, stress of face sheet and core and impact energy.

Fig. 5 1/4" symmetric model and boundary condition of AHSP

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3-point bending test

As shown in Fig. 6(a), in the short-edge direction wrinkle of core emitted the low signal at 0~1.5sec. Then several burst signals engenders and debonding is starting at inner face sheet from 1.5~3.5sec. Because of friction between upper and lower face sheet, continuous burst signal appeared at 3.5~5.5sec. Lower face sheet began tearing at 5.5~7.5sec. As shown in Fig. 6(b), in the long-edge direction burst signal appeared because of fracture of lower face sheet at 0~1.5sec. Large signal occurred to core tear at 1.5~3.5sec.

Fig. 6 AE counts for 1/2" size cell specimen : (a) short-edge direction, (b) long-edge direction

Impact test

Fig. 7 shows torn specimen observed after impact by naked eye, (a) 34J in face, (b) 21J in long-edge, (c) short-edge, (d) point, damaged at 19J. The fracture mode of AHSP under stronger impact force is indicated in Fig. 9 at the site of face, long-edge, point, and short-edge.

Fig. 7 Visible Damage (a)face, (b)long-edge, (c)short-edge, (d)point

Results in Fig. 8 express the typical fracture modes of honeycomb specimen that is damaged by impact position.

Fig. 8 Typical fracture mode of AHSP : (a)face, (b)long-edge, (c)short-edge, (d)point

After initial tear happens to the point or edge of core at the impact energy of 43J, face sheet begins to be depression as shown figure (a). In 43J penetration happens. 6 adjacency cores transmit impact load adequately from the face Which doesn't tear the face sheet under 10J, 19J, 32J. Figure (b) and (c) display the damaged specimen of long edge, short edge each in 32J. Fracture mode develops. Core cuts into face sheet when the limit load level is exceeded at the edges and tile fracture is transmitted by linked 4 edges. This certifies that the fracture of edge is the reason of final penetration. furthermore, long edge appears to be stronger under impact than short edge for 4 long edges are linked by 4 short edges. Figure (d) illustrates the impact mode at point under impact energy 32J. Embayment and buckling occur in face sheet similarly with (b) and (c). While the support load at point exceed the limit, tear happens to face sheet along 3 edges by pinning of the core.

Impact load data report that the curve related in hysteresis or impact load-time displays similar tendency to impact load-deflection curve. When 11.9kg_f impact three is applied to AHSP by 1/2" cell, impulsive load appears increasing tendency with the increases of impact energy (Fig. 10). As shown in figure (a), the impact load-time curves show the similar results for 4 impact positions under impact energy of 10J. In figure (b), the curves give resembling result under 19J. Result of impact load expressed large difference under 32J, 43J which is illustrated in figure (c), (d). The impact energy of 10J and 19J cannot give great damage to AHSP. But under 32J and 43J the impact loads create considerable crash at face, long-edge, and point and short edge. After delivering enough shear force by adjacency core face sheet of lower part suffered high impact force from rebounding of the core damage. Buckling occurs

to edge and point because of the shear force and upper-part or lower-part face sheet tears by this buckling.

Fig. 9 Impact load of 1/2" AHSP cell corresponding to 11.9kg_f impactor

Similarly, the curves with impact load of 11.9kg_f and 5.25kg_f are shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. The cell size is 1/2". The values of impact load of 5.25kg_f and 11.9kg_f in equal 1/2" specimen appear to have the similar tendency. But because of the unequal weight and different impact height, the impact is imposed for the increased final speed. As shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, for 11.9kg_f impact load the speed reaching to maximum impact load is 8.5m/sec for 10J, 8m/sec for 19J, 4~8m/sec for 32J, 4~6m/sec for 43J. For 5.25kg_f impact load the impact speed of is 5.5m/sec, 4~6m/sec, 3~5m/sec for 10J, 19J, 32J, 43J respectively, which is much faster than the first case. It invokes larger strain energy and produce bigger damage area. We know the impact energy is the function of speed. But from the data above we can find that the weight is more dominant element of impact behavior than speed.

Fig. 10 Impact load of 1/2" AHSP cell corresponding to 5.25kg_f impactor

By comparing Fig. 9 and Fig. 10, we also can find that the impact curves of 1/4" and 1/2" cell display the resembling tendency.

Absorbed energy

The maximum absorption energy is marked as E_a in the absorbed energy curve, which leads to the damage of AHSP. The amount of absorbed energy dedicated to the damage is marked as E_l , and the remaining elastic energy is marked as E_e .

Fig. 11 is the graph of absorption energy obtained by 32J impact energy toward 1/2" cell's honeycomb panel with impact tup of 11.9kg_f and 5.25kg_f, respectively. The elastic energy of face and long-edge is shown in figure (a) under 11.9kg_f impact damage. In figure (b) elastic energy curves of face, long-edge as well as point are illustrated under 5.25kg_f. It can be clearly observed that weight has an obvious effect on the impact damage, that is, heavier weight will produce larger damage.

Fig. 11 Absorbed energy of 1/2" AHSP cell corresponding to 32J

Whole absorption energy curves display similar results regardless of impact position in 10, 19J. The impact resistance is increasing by the order of face, long edge, point and short edge in 32, 43J, which can be observed in the cases of existence and nonexistence of elastic energy. The short edge elastic energy appears less than 11.9kg_f. This means that the impact energy that the short edge can suffer is lower than 11.9kg_f.

Ultrasonic c-scan is known as a useful method to observe damage face size after impact. Fig. 12 shows the c-scan figure of the damage surface. From this figure we can find that the afloat area of 11.9kg_f impact force with 32J impact energy in 1/2" cell size's specimen is larger than that of 5.25kg_f. This means that heavy impact tup creates big damage face about the same impact energy, which explains that impact experiment data and c-scan image agree well.

Fig. 12 Ultrasonic c-scan image corresponding to impactor types

Finite elements analysis

Nonlinear analysis about each impact energy that use impact tup of 11.9kg_f and 5.25kg_f about 1/2" cell is performed by finite element method. Fig. 13(a) show Von Mises stress of the case of 11.9kg_f impact force and 32J impact energy in 1/2" cell specimen. Maximum stress 133.8MPa happens to the face sheet that tup is touched. Fig. 13(b) displays stress distribution that interacts with the core. The maximum in the core is about 58.1Mpa. When impact acts to the face, large stress impose on the edge and joints of edge and the stress is transmitted by contiguity core. In Fig. 14, with the increase of impact energy, the maximum stress happens in face sheet. The stress transmitted through the core is decrescent. While the impact speed quickens, stress concentration is happened locally at impact position before damage is transmitted. Comparing Fig. 14 (a) and (b), stress of the core is larger in the case of 11.9kg_f than that of 5.25kg_f under the same impact energy. This analysis data also agree with the experimental results and c-scan image. Furthermore, the impact tup of 5.25kg_f of the faster speed generates yielding stress into face sheet with shorter time.

Fig. 13 Von Mises stress of AHSP corresponding to 32J : (a) at facesheet, (b) at core

Fig. 16 Stress and time of impact energy by 5.25kg_f and 11.9kg_f impactor

CONCLUSIONS

Bending tests using acoustic emission method and finite element analysis are proposed in order to study the impact behavior of face sheet and core of Aluminum Honeycomb Sandwich Panel (AHSP). Summaries of the research are as follows.

Damage mode at 3-points bending test using AE count is analyzed. By the result, the tear of lower-part face sheet happens while preserve bending forces were applied at the core early in the short-edge direction. After lower-part face sheet of long-edge tears, separation of core and face sheet occur. Therefore, Short edges in the honeycomb structure receive more bending forces.

Impact behaviors for various AHSP's positions are similar under low impact energy. However, in high impact energy it is different by the positions such as AHSP's face, long-

edge, point and short-edge, Face is strongest to suffer the impact. And thickness is also an important factor to prevent tear of upper-part and lower-part face sheet.

Under the same impact energy, heavy impact tup needs more time to reach the maximum impact load than light impact tup. The strain energy is much larger for heavy tup. The wider damage area is engendered which is confirmed by c-scan image. This means that low-speed impact is dominated by the effect of weight.

According to finite element analysis of impact behavior, if the speed is the faster, the time that reaches the maximum stress is shortened by increasing the speed. Impact damage increases locally, which explains that the speed is the main variable to generate localized damage.

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